

A Study of Ivory & Bone Sculptural Art of Bengal

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Abstract

Ivory carving is a centuries-old Indian art. Since prehistoric times, India has sculpted ivory and bone into ornaments. Ivory carving was regarded as a noble vocation and a premium craft in these parts. Ivory items have been discovered at Harappan sites. A thriving city with a population of creative energy in many professions also aids the growth of any craft. Bone combined with ivory has been utilised for both utilitarian and ornamental purposes since prehistoric times.

Key Words: Bone, Ivory Art, Bengal.

Introduction

Ivory craft is a very ancient craft of India. India has ornamentally carved ivory & bone since pre-historic times. Here ivory carvings were considered as a noble profession and the craft was a deluxe craft. Evidences of ivory objects are found from Harappan sites.

A flourishing city with a population of the creative energy in various fields also helps any craft to flourish. Bone with ivory has also been used from ancient times for making utility articles as well as decorative ones.

Epigraphic evidence: - A votive inscription from Sanchi Stupa on southern gateway mentions that the ivory carvers (*danta-karehi*) of Vidisa carved the figures of these gateway. This record reflects that during the first century B.C ivory-craft and trade-guild of the ivory carvers was flourished in these areas. So much so that readily lent their free-services for the sculptural embellishment of the said gateway. (Dwivedi, 1976:16)

The second evidence comes from Bengal. The Bhatara copper-plate inscription from the village Bhatara, now in Bangladesh, records that an ivory worker of a nearby village was attached in establishment of a Siva temple by the king. So, it is apparent that the craft was held in high respect and ivory objects were used in the temple. (Dwivedi, 1976: 17)

Another inscription, the Edilpur (District Faridpur, now in Bangladesh) Copper Plate inscription of Kesava Sena describes that king Balla Sena (1168-1169 A.D) carried away the fortune goddess of his enemies on palanquins resting on staffs made of elephant tusks. Fortune goddess either means the idols of gods and goddesses of his enemies or the treasures of them.

Literary References: - In the Vedic literature there are no direct references of ivory craft, surprisingly though Vedic society was well acquainted with elephants and several words have been used for elephant- *Ibha*, *naga*, *mrigavarana* and *hastin*. Some scholars are of opinion that the word ‘ivory’ is derived from the word ‘*ibha*’, means elephant. (Dwivedi, 1976:17)

Rig Veda has mentioned about a gambler and the brown dice. It is known to all that dice was generally made of ivory and it takes a brownish colour with time and by constant handling. (Dwivedi, 1976: 18.)

In *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata*, we often noticed the references of ivory and ivory carvers.

In *Ramayana* *Ravana*'s palace in *Lanka* was decorated with ivory works-it had ivory inlaid floors, pillars, windows etc. Hanuman during his search for Sita noticed *Ravana*'s bed, *rathas* were embellished with Ivory works. In the age of *Ramayana* palanquins and others wooden objects specially furniture was also adorned with ivory works. Even royal umbrellas which described as white in the Epic were probably heavily decorated with ivory. In *Ayodhyakanda* of the *Ramayana* the inhabitants of the city are represented as going out in procession with *Bharat* to seek *Rama* in the forest, in the order of the trade-guilds: - “Jewellers, potters, ivory workers, perfumers, gold-smiths, weavers, carpenters, painters, black-smiths, copper-smiths etc....”(Dutta, 1901: 1).

The *Mahabharata* gives more explicit information about ivory carvings of its age. The king of *Pragjyotisa* (*Assam*) presented *Yudhisthira* many swords with handle made of pure ivory on the occasion of *Rajasuya* sacrifice. From another reference we come to know that kings of *Magadha*, *Bengal* and *Orissa* gifted *Yudhisthira* valuable furnitures with inlay works of ivory, gold and semiprecious stones. The royal thrones were also embellished with ivory works. (Dwivedi, 1976:19.) Another very important information about the use of ivory is provided in the *Karnaparva* of the *Mahabharata*. It mentions *Duryadhana* anointing *Karna* as his *Senapati* by pouring on his head holy water contained in elephant's tusk. Pouring holy water on the head of the anointed was an ancient custom employed in the *Rajasuya* and *Abhiseka* ceremonies. (Dwivedi, 1976:19)

Arthasastra of *Kautilya* often mentioned about ivory and several ivory dices have been recovered from the excavation in the *Mauryan* phase.

Silavanga Jataka mentions about ivory-workers' market at *Banaras*. The existence of a separate market of ivory –carvers shows that ivory products had certain popularity and the quantum of trade in them was large enough to support a full-fledged market. *Chhandanta Jataka* tale points to the great demand for elephant ivory.

In *Buddha Charita* by Asvaghosa (2nd century A.D) it is interesting to notice the mention of a palanquin embellished with ivory works. It also says that when Bodhisattva was an elephant, his tusks were cut seven times. Working with ivory appears to have been a recognised profession in most of ancient India's major towns.

Milindapanha informs us about the contemporary occupation of ivory-carvings.

Sudraka in *Mricchakatikam*, mentioned a high resplendent archway is encrusted with ivory.

In Kalidasa's *Raghuvamsa* we find references to an ivory-ear-scroll which has been compared to a pale-white ketaka flower petal. (Dwivedi, 1976:22.) In *Meghaduta* Kalidasa compares the whiteness of Mount Kailash with that of a freshly cut elephant tusk.

The *Periplus of the Erythraean Sea* (1st century CE) mentioned that India had flourishing trade in ivory with Rome.

Apart from these texts *Mahavastu*, *Divyavadana*, *Kamasutra* of *Vatsayana*, *Vishnudharmottara Purana* and *Brihatsamhita* of Gupta period, jain text *Angavijja*, datable to 4th-5th century CE, *Harshacharita* and *Kadambari* of *Bana* there are ample references of ivory works and these texts mention the existence of ivory craft in urban centres of India. It can be assumed that in early times the craft of ivory carvings was conditioned to a large extent by the availability of ivory. Also, a strong centralised power with several urban centres created a congenial condition for ivory and other deluxe crafts to flourish was needed.

In eastern India bone-ivory craft meant for ornamental and decorative purpose have been found mainly during Sunga-Kushan period. From ancient period till now bone-ivory plays an important role in the magico-religious beliefs of people of Indian sub-continent for the aversion of evil, death and misfortune.

In early ivory & bone carvings of Bengal woman figures and orgiastic group have been found in many parts of undivided Bengal. Woman plays an important role in magico-sexual rites which are performed with a view to increasing the fertility of the soil and vegetation, to bringing rain and in general to assuring agricultural fruitfulness. In contemporary terracotta art of Bengal we have similar types of fertility goddesses but in comparison as a precious craft ivory was produced for a few selected elite citizens.

Types of Ivory-The term 'ivory', though loosely applied to the tooth structure of the elephant, walrus, hippopotamus, whale and some others, is strictly speaking, confined to the dentine present only in the tusks of the elephant.

The teeth of hippopotamus are another source of ivory. These are denser, and have a closer grain than elephant ivory and are the hardest of all teeth used as ivory. The only limitation in this kind of ivory is that it can be used for small work alone because of its size and does not have the pattern of crossing lines. In colour it is pure white. (Dwivedi, 1976: 3)

The source of walrus ivory are the long tusks hanging perpendicularly downwards from the upper jaw of the animal. This sea animal resembles a seal and is found in the arctic regions.

The tusks of the walrus are much larger than those of the hippopotamus are generally oval in section. However, the walrus tusks do not have the fine intersecting lines of elephant ivory. (Dwivedi, 1976: 3.)

A sub-variety of walrus ivory is 'beach ivory'. The name is given by the Alaskans to the fossil tusks of walrus.

Dugong ivory is a local variety of ivory used for carvings in Java, Sumatra and Philippines. The kind of ivory principally comes from the female sea-cow which outwardly does not appear to bear tusks. But inside the skull are huge tusks. The tusks of the male sea-cow have a deep basal cavity and prominent surface scoring, both of which reduce the amount of usable ivory. (Dwivedi, p-3)

Whale's teeth ivory came into use rather late. It can be easily be recognised by the short, stubby shape of the whale teeth, their broadly rounded ends, and their conical base cavities.

Asia and Africa are the two main ivory-producing continents, but their products differ considerably owing to climatic and geographical factors.

Difference between bone and ivory– Bone as a special material was easily used by men from the pre-historic age for technical and domestic purpose. The *Jatakas* tell us that bones, particularly monkey's bones were used frequently for children's necklaces. Structurally, it is less fibrous but more brittle than ivory, and splinters easily. So, the use of bone was restricted of awls, knives, kohl-sticks and mirror handles etc. The main difference between ivory and bone-which makes ivory more suitable for carvings than bone- is that there is an oily or waxy solution in the pores of ivory.

From different periods and different regions of India ivory objects have been reported though early ivory finds are restricted to utilitarian items such as combs, hairpins and arrowheads etc. Evidences of its existence are found in Harappan Cultural sites (*Circa* 2500-1500 B.C) of Western and North-Western India. (census p5)

Ivory seal set in a copper circlet has found from the monastery mound at Shah-ji-ki-dheri near Peshawar. Ivory seals and sealings have been found in Bhita near Allahabad, Nalanda and other Buddhist sites. (Ajit Ghosh, Rupam. p 122-129)

Excavations conducted in different regions of India have yielded many objects from different historical phases. The Kushana period shows the high-water mark of Indian ivory/bone carvings, the huge quantity discovered at Taxila and Begram indicated the popularity of the ivory medium during this period. (Dwivedi, 1976: 94.) Moreover, Begram was the summer capital of the Kushanas whose domain included Afghanistan.

Conclusion

The Chandraketugarh discoveries, which exhibit a broad array of items ranging from common hairpins and combs to sword handles and ivory dices, indicate that ivory was used for a variety of purposes in Bengal. For instance, beautiful carvings depicting mithuna, divine female figures and shalabhanjika or tree goddess.

The Mauryan sculptures and appliqué terracottas have been well defined by scholars. No such definite characteristics can be attributed to the ivories of this period. During this period ivory was used for producing seals and conventional items like arrow-heads, dice, hair-pins, kohl sticks etc. (Dwivedi, 1976: 60.)

The Sunga period has a very important place in the development of Indian Art. In Mauryan period the patronage of art was practised by the Mauryan court only. (Dwivedi, 1976:61.) But in the Sunga period it passed on to the commoners whose names are inscribed on the Bharhut, Bodhgaya, and Sanchi monuments. These three places represented the first organised art activity of the Indian people as a whole. The human figure is endowed with a new form and bearing. In the field of terracotta, moulds came into use for the first time, which meant greater accuracy and mass production. (Dwivedip, 61.)

In the field of ivory and bone, excavations have brought to light more objects of this period than the earlier ones. (Dwivedi, 1976: 62.)

It has been mentioned earlier that Kushana period was famous for ivory sculptures. The political, social and economic condition helped the craft to flourish. The Kushana period is marked by the prolonged and fruitful co-existence of the various people who inhabited the empire and of their traditions, religious system and beliefs. At this very time Roman trade with Asia was almost at its peak. There was a free flow of travellers from one place to another. Many professions are known from literary and epigraphic records. Flourishing trade and consequent prosperity were instrumental in supplying a prolific patronage of arts, which attained a new height under the Kushanas.

It is evident that the Gupta artists were not very productive in the medium of ivory and only a few ivory objects can be assigned to this period all over India. This is rather surprising as it is during the Gupta period that India was at the height of prosperity and artistic achievements.

In late medieval period the principal centre of ivory carvings in Bengal was Murshidabad. In those days the industry received patronization of the Nawabs and the noblemen of the court. Ivory craft of Murshidabad mainly followed a style exclusively developed in Bengal. The Bengal ivory-craftsmen acquired considerable proficiency in bone-ivory carvings. Decorative pieces of ivory carvings of Murshidabad were displayed in the museums across the world.

Majority of the ivory-bone objects of our collection belong to the Medieval and Late-Medieval period and most of them collected from districts of Murshidabad.

The only district of West Bengal in which the art of ivory carvings was practised a few decades ago is Murshidabad. Formerly they enjoyed rent-free holdings of the lands. But after the Independence Government of India declared ivory-trade illegal, the industry, on which they lived in affluence, is now lost much of the skill their ancestors possessed.

Some bone and ivory sculptures in the collection of State Archaeological Museum. West Bengal.

1. Handle of a knife, cylindrical in shape, showing a man and two women are standing in a row-(10.2cm x2.4 cm) South 24 Parganas. West Bengal. Period- Sunga. (1st century B.C)

This bone object probably depicts a scene of performance of fertility festival. The central figure is a female figure standing her left in akimbo and right hand touches the hand of another woman. Here she is most probably the principal figure. She wears a transparent lower garment through which her genital part is clearly visible and torque, bangles and anklets. Below on her left side a swan is appeared in profile, looks upwards. Another female figure is standing under a pillar with her both hands outstretched. She is holding bell like objects which are hanging from the pillar. She wears a two tired conical head gear with a circular object on the top, circular earrings, transparent lower garment up to knee, anklets and beaded waist girdle. A scarf-like object is visible hanging from the left side of her waist. The only male is also standing with two outstretched hands and his right is bent slightly at the knee-joint. The right hand of the male figure touches the body of the central female figure and the left hand touches a decorative hanging from the above. He wears circular earrings, necklace and beaded waistbands and bangles and armlets. He also wears anklets. His head-dress is simple but interesting, decorated with eye-shaped object, probably a leaf designed hair pin.

2. Bone plaque. Mongalkot, Bardhaman. West Bengal-(15.6cmx7.2cm) Period, Sunga-Kushana. (Circa 1st century B.C)

This plaque from Malgolkot is carved out of a fossilized bone. This fragmental plaque depicts probably a toilet scene. It is work of rich taste and shows a profound felling for slender form and graceful rhythmic expression. The plaque has carvings on both side of it. A female is sitting on a mat with both the legs folded from the knee. The right leg rests on the mat and the right-hand rests on the left upright folded knee.

She has a knotted hair-do, wears a heavy necklace which is hanging in between her two heavy breasts. She also wears a waist girdle, frilled lower garment and heavy anklets. Behind her there standing two head-less figures. The figure just behind the seated female figure is probably a female, because it has a very slender waistband a deep naval. It wears a heavy necklace and a waist girdle. The back side of the plaque shows two standings wearing dhoti with frilled hanging ends.

3. Bone Plaque, Chandraketugarh, North 24 Parganas. West Bengal. (7.8cmx4.6cm).Period: Sunga-Kushana.

This bone plaque depicts the scene of performance of fertility rites. A female figure is standing under a tree. Below there are two figures. The figure that stands is offering some fruits to the seated figure. There is also an offering bowl. The seated figure sits with his legs folded and his outstretched right hand is receiving the offer. In Indian art fertility scenes are very common. But either in stone or in terracotta these types of narratives details are not very common, at in Bengal art.

4. Female Figure. Bone. Chandraketugarh. North 24 Parganas. West Bengal. (Height- 5.6cm) .Period- Circa 4th Century A.D - The figure shows a standing female carved in round. She has prominent breasts and genital organ. She wears waist girdle, a transparent lower garment up to knee and anklets. Her hair tied like a knot and some parts hanging from her left, the end of which she holds with her left hand.

5. Durga Mahisasuramardini. Murshidabad. West Bengal.Period Circa late 19th Century CE (17.5 cm X 15 cm). An intricately carved ten-armed ivory image of Mahisasuramardi, accompanied by her four children. She is slaying the Mahisaura. The sculpture is placed on a rectangular pedestal with an intricately carved Chalchitra.

6. Lord Ganesh. Bengal. Period- Circa 19th Century CE. (Height- 11.2 cm)Standing ivory image of four-armed lord Ganesha on an octagonal lotus pedestal with his lower right hand shows *varada mudra*. The Lord holds a conch shell and a flower in his upraised right and left hand respectively. He is also holding a *Modaka* in his lower left hand. Mushika the mount is visible near his left foot

7. Goddess Kali- Bengal.Period-Circa 19th Century CE. (11.9 cm X 10 cm). An ivory image of four handed goddess Kali trampling on Shiva. She is wearing a 'mundamala' (garland of human skull) and a waist belt of human skull and bone.

8. Clam shell– Murshidabad. West Bengal. Period-Circa 19th Century CE. (12.9 cm X 5 cm)An ivory object depicting scenes of Ramayana's in Ravana's Asoka garden.

9. Ivory comb-Bengal. Period- Circa 18th century CE. (7cm X 6.3 cm). An ivory comb with figures of Goddess Lakshmi & Saraswati at the half circular butt-end. Goddess Lakshmi is accompanied by her vahana owl in the background of a cornfield while Goddess Saraswati is represented in the background of 'Kamala Vana' (Lotus forest)

10. Goddess Durga with her two attendants. Murshidabad. Period- Circa 19th century CE. (7.2 X 9.5cm). An ivory image of two-armed Goddess with her two female attendants Jaya & Vijaya on both sides. This type of Durga images are also known as 'Abhaya'.

11. Female Deity. Murshidabad, West Bengal. Period-Circa 19th century CE. (7.4 cm X 6.8 cm) An ivory image of a four-armed female deity adorned with jewellery, crown and sari, seated on a tiger and trampling on an elephant.

12. A votive bone Plaque in the shape of a trident. West Bengal. Period-Circa 18th Century CE. (15.90cm)A votive plaque with carvings on both sides. The upper part delineates Lord Brahma flanked by goddess Lakshmi and Saraswati on both sides. Lower part on one side shows seated four-armed Lord Vishnu with his consort and holding Chakra & Shanka in upper two hands, his lower two hands are resting on his knees. The other side shows seated four-armed Lord Shiva with his consort and holding *trisula* & *damaru* in his upper two hands.

13. A votive bone plaque with carvings on both sides. Eastern India. Period- Circa 18th century CE. (5.8 cm X 10.9 cm) Obverse delineates *Sesanagsayane* Vishnu with his consort Lakshmi. Lord Brahma is seated on a lotus, the long stem of which originates from Vishnu's navel. The reverse bears a scene of pleasure trip on a stylised boat. The central figure represents a king with horns accompanied by his female attendants.

14. Brooch- Murshidabad. West Bengal. Period- Circa 19th century CE. (4.3 cm X 3 cm) A delicately carved ivory brooch with tin frame depicting a religious scene.

15. Figure of an infant. Kolkata. West Bengal. Period-Circa late 19th Century CE. (Height- 8.9 cm)Ivory figure of a standing naked male infant chewing the index finger of his right hand.

16. Six Ivory Female Musicians standing on semi-circular pedestal, wearing ghagra-choli playing different types of musical instruments. Murshidabad. West Bengal. Period- Circa late 19th Century CE (Height – approx. 7.8 cm) from left to right.

- (i) Female figure playing flute.
- (ii) Female figure playing small drums (Dugi in Bengali) attached to her waist band.
- (iii) Female figure playing mridangam.
- (iv) Female figure playing tambura/vina.
- (v) Female figure playing esraj.
- (vi) Female figure playing cymbals/ karatal.

17. Bullock Cart. Murshidabad. West Bengal. Period- Circa 19th century CE. (11.5 cm X 6.1 cm) Beautifully carved ivory bullock cart drawn by two bulls and driven by a man wearing pagri/headdress.

18. Well caparisoned elephant with howdah. Murshidabad. West Bengal. Period -Circa 19th century CE. (10.2 cm X 4.6 cm). Well caparisoned (intricately carved cloth covering) ivory elephant with howdah and two noble men seated inside it. The Mahut is sitting on the head of the elephant. This delicately carved ivory sculpture is placed on a rectangular very thin pedestal.

19. Ivory miniature carvings of two elephants grazing in a jungle. Bengal. Period- Circa early 19th century CE. (3.8 cm X 3.7 cm) & (4.7 cm X 4.5 cm).

20. An ivory boat. Murshidabad. West Bengal. Period- Circa 19th century CE. (length 15 cm)- Miniature ivory boat with sail placed on a wooden pedestal.

21. Mayurpankhi boat (Peacock faced). Harynarayanpur. South 24 Parganas. West Bengal. Period- Circa early 20th century CE. (Length-29.5 cm) A nobleman and his sailors ride on a wooden mayurpankhi (peacock faced) boat. The human figures are made of ivory.

22. An ivory glass- Bengal. Period- Circa 19th century CE. (7.4 cm X 3.4 cm) A small ivory glass with vertical flutings all through the outer surface.

23. Mughal Soldiers. Murshidabad. West Bengal. Circa late 18th century CE. (Height approx. 4.5 cm)

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The illustrations of the above objects are given below

Figure 1 Bone handle of a knife. 24 Pgs (south)

Figure 2 Fossilized Bone plaque. Mangolkot.

Figure 3 Bone plaque.CKG

Figure 4 Bone female Figure CKG

Figure 5 Ivory Durga Mahisasuramardini. Murshidabad

Figure 6 Ivory Lord Ganesh

Figure 7 Ivory Goddess Kali. Bengal

Figure 8 Ivory Clam shell. Murshidabad

Figure 9 Ivory comb, Bengal

Figure 10 Ivory Durga with her two female Attendant
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Figure 11 Ivory female deity. Murshidabad

Figure 12A votive bone plaque obverse & reverse. (Two photos)

Figure 13 Votive bone plaque. Eastern India

Figure 14 Ivory Brooch. Murshidabad

Figure 15 Ivory Figure of an infant, Kolkata

Figure 16 Six Ivory female musicians, Murshidabad

Figure 17 Ivory bullock cart. Murshidabad

Figure 18 Well caparisoned elephant with howdah. (Ivory)

Figure 19 Two Ivory elephants. Bengal

Figure 20 An Ivory boat with sail. Murshidabad

Figure 1Figure 21. Mayurpankhi boat. Harynarayanpur.24 PGS (south).

Figure 22. An ivory glass. Bengal

Figure 23. Ivory Mughal soldiers. Murshidabad.

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